

New Therapeutic Agents of the Quinoline Series: Part II. Quinoline Compounds with Basic Side Chains

B. Behra, P. C. Rath and M. K. Rout

Several hydroxy and amino-quinolines have been condensed with diethylaminoethyl chloride hydrochloride, β bromoethylamine hydrobromide, piperidinoethyl chloride hydrochloride, morpholinoethyl chloride and chloroacetyl chloride, followed by condensation with diethylamine. The hydrochlorides of these compounds have been tested for their antispasmodic and antihistaminic properties.

Based on the current theory of antispasmodic action¹ and the antispasmodic activity of quinoline compounds², it was considered of interest to investigate the spasmolytic activity of compounds prepared by condensing amino- and hydroxy-quinolines with β -diethylaminoethyl chloride hydrochloride etc. In these compounds the latter components furnish the tertiary or the quaternary nitrogen head which acts as the first focus, whereas the former, i.e., the quinoline ring with an O or N side-chain possessing a lone pair on oxygen or nitrogen serves as the second focus. These compounds are therefore expected to provide a protective shield not only on account of their size but also due to their ability to tolerate the positive charge because of high resonance stability of the resulting cations which will lead to a greater electron density at the second focus thus assisting the compound to fasten to the receptor surface effectively.

In the present communication, ten quinoline derivatives were prepared. The details of their syntheses are described in the experimental part.

The spasmolytic activities of the ammonium salts of the compounds against acetylcholine chloride and histamine acid phosphate spasm of isolated Guinea-pig ileum have been determined by the Magnus method and the results show that most of these compounds have antispasmodic and antihistaminic action without any side reaction and the activities of some of these compounds are comparable with the standard antispasmodic and antihistaminic drugs now in clinical use.

EXPERIMENTAL

8-Diethylaminoacetoxyquinoline.—This involved the preparation of the intermediate 8-chloroacetoxyquinoline, which was synthesised as follows: To 8-hydroxy quinoline (1.3 g.), dissolved in chloroform (15 ml), chloroacetyl chloride (1.2 ml) was added. Reaction took place immediately with evolution of heat and separation of a solid. The whole mixture

1. Lands et. al., *J. Pharmacol. Exptl. Therap.*, 1956, 117, 331.

2. A. V. Tolstoukhov, "Ionic interpretation of Drug Action in Chemotherapeutic Research, Chemical Publishing Co. New York, 1955, p. 55.

was refluxed on a water bath for 2 hr. at 70°. Excess of the solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the solid obtained was filtered, washed thoroughly with water and finally re-crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 127°, yield 68%. (Found: Cl, 16.25. $C_{11}H_{10}O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 17.06%).

To the above 8-chloroacetoxyquinoline (1.04 g.), diethylamine (0.4 g.) was added and the mixture was refluxed on a water bath at 70° for 10 hr. Excess of diethylamine present was removed by heating on a water bath when a heavy black oil was left behind. This was taken up in ether through which dry hydrogen chloride gas was passed for a few seconds. The dihydro-chloride of 8-diethylaminoacetoxyquinoline separating was filtered, washed with dry ether and finally re-crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 194°; yield 50%. (Found: Cl, 21.29. $C_{13}H_{20}O_2N_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 21.45%).

The analytical data etc. of other diethylaminoacetoxyquinoline hydrochlorides and diethylaminoacetamidoquinoline hydrochlorides are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

N,N-Diethylaminoacetoxy and *N,N*-diethylaminoacetamido quinoline dihydrochlorides.

No.	Compound	X	M.P.	Yield	% Chlorine	
					Found	Reqd.
1.	3-R. Q.	-NH-	234°	80%	21.43	21.52
2.	8-R. Q.	-NH-	196°	55	21.39	21.52
3.	6-R. Q.	-NH-	302°	50	21.37	21.52
4.	8-R. Q.	-O-	194°	81	21.21	21.45
5.	4-Methyl 2-R. Q.	-O-	211°	66	20.43	20.58
6.	4,6-Dimethyl 2-R. Q.	-O-	240°	72	19.71	19.78
7.	4,8-Dimethyl 2-R. Q.	-O-	212°	78	19.63	19.78
8.	2-Methyl 4-R. Q.	-O-	194°	67	20.52	20.58

Q = Quinoline, X = -O-, -NH-

Substituted Aminoquinolines:—The condensation reactions were carried out in the following manner.

The mixture of the aminoquinoline (0.1M) and the disubstituted aminoalkyl chloride hydrochloride (0.11M) was either refluxed in dry acetone in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate or the free disubstituted aminoalkyl chloride and the aminoquinoline were refluxed in absolute ethanol at 70-80° for 12 to 15 hr. The resulting mixture was then poured on water and made strongly alkaline with sodium hydroxide. After cooling, the liberated base was taken in ether and the ethereal solution dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate. The ether was removed by evaporation on a steam-bath and finally *in vacuo*.

The free bases were dissolved either in absolute ethanol, dry benzene or dry ether (sodium) depending on their solubility in these solvents and converted to the dihydrochloride.

rides by saturation with dry hydrogen chloride gas. Recrystallisations were effected from ethanol-ether.

The same procedure was used for the preparation of derivatives of hydroxy-quinolines.

For analysis, the dihydrochlorides were dried *in vacuo* at 100° for 1 hr. The analytical data etc. of the dihydrochlorides are recorded in Tables II-V.

TABLE II

β-Aminoethoxy- and β-aminoethylamino-quinoline dihydrochlorides.

No.	Compounds	X	M.P.	Yield	% Chlorine	
					Found	Reqd.
1.	3-R. Q	-NH-	193°	65%	27.21	27.31
2.	5-R. Q	-NH-	225°	55	27.26	27.31
3.	6-R. Q	-NH-	> 320°	81	27.19	27.31
4.	8-R. Q	-NH-	171°(d)	67	27.07	27.31
5.	8-R. Q	-O-	222°	78	27.11	27.20
6.	4-Methyl 2-R. Q	-O-	219°	65	25.68	25.82
7.	4,6-Dimethyl 2-R. Q	-O-	226°	70	24.49	24.57
8.	4,8-Dimethyl 2-R. Q	-O-	202°	72	24.53	24.57
9.	2-Methyl 4-R. Q	-O-	> 303°	66	25.78	25.82

X = -O-, -NH-; Q = quinoline..

d denotes decomposition

TABLE III

β-N, N-Diethylaminoethoxy- and (β-NN-diethylaminoethyl)-aminoquinoline hydrochlorides.

No	Compounds	X	M.P.	Yield	% Chlorine	
					Found	Reqd.
1.	3-R. Q	-NH-	232°	65%	22.29	22.47
2.	8-R. Q	-NH-	182°	65	22.43	22.47
3.	6-R. Q	-NH-	> 310°	58	22.37	22.47
4.	5-R. Q	-NH-	> 310°	63	22.39	22.47
5.	8-R. Q	-O-	53°	80	22.17	22.40
6.	4-Methyl 2-R. Q	-O-	180°	68	20.98	21.45
7.	4,6-Dimethyl 2-R. Q	-O-	208°	62	20.32	20.58
8.	4,8-Dimethyl 2-R. Q	-O-	253	75	20.35	20.58
9.	2-Methyl 4-R. Q	-O-	86°	68	21.21	21.45

X = -O-, -NH-, Q = Quinoline.

TABLE IV

Piperidinoethoxy- and piperidinoethylamino quinoline hydrochlorides.

No.	Compounds	X.	M.P.	Yield.	% Chlorine	
					Found	Reqd
1.	3-R. Q	-NH-	193-95°	56%	21.59	21.65
2.	6-R. Q	-NH-	> 300°	49	21.54	21.65
3.	8-R. Q	-NH-	89°	66	21.63	21.65
4.	4-Methyl 2-R. Q	-O-	165°	73	20.37	20.70
5.	4,6-Dimethyl 2-R. Q	-O-	194°	75	19.55	19.89
6.	4,8-Dimethyl 2-R. Q	-O-	185°	59	19.68	19.89
7.	8-R. Q	-O-	226°	68	21.39	21.58

X = -O-, -NH-; Q = Quinoline

TABLE V

Morpholinoethoxy- and morpholinoethylamino-quinoline-hydrochlorides.

No	Compounds	X.	M.P.	Yield	% Chlorine	
					Found	Reqd.
1.	3-R. Q	-NH-	174°	67%	21.38	21.52
2.	6-R. Q	-NH-	> 300°	72	21.50	21.52
3.	8-R. Q	-NH-	> 300°	78	21.41	21.52
4.	4-Methyl 2-R. Q	-O-	170°	65	20.35	20.58
5.	4,8-Dimethyl 2-R. Q	-O-	206°	56	19.39	19.78
6.	4,6-Dimethyl 2-R. Q	-O-	148°	48	19.58	19.78
7.	8-R. Q	-O-	231°	61	21.36	21.45

X = -O-, -NH-; Q = Quinoline

The authors are grateful to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi, and to the Board of Scientific and Industrial Research, Orissa, for financial assistance to carry out this investigation.